

Perception of Policy Holders Towards Life Insurance Corporation Scheme in Salem City

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ABSTRACT

India's agricultural population struggles to save money due to low earnings. Investors prioritize immediate needs over saving for the future. Life insurance is actually an agreement between the insured and the insurer, in which the policyholder accepts to pay the insurer a regular premium. In return, the insurer provides monetary protection to the insured in the event of any accident or mishap. This study investigates policyholders' Economic development with the Life Insurance Corporation's financial expansion in Thanjavur City. This study identifies policyholder's economic growth and their impact in LIC programs, highlighting the importance of the insurance sector in modern economies for saving habits and protection. Data was collected through a questionnaire and practical sampling strategy with 200 participants.

Keywords: Satisfaction, Economic Growth, Life Insurance Corporation

INTRODUCTION

High-performance companies have developed principles and strategies to achieve customer satisfaction. A framework using customer satisfaction principles and strategies can improve quality responsiveness and support residents in vulnerable communities in providing services in the public sector. This study examines students' perceptions of online learning during the pandemic, focusing on universities. It highlights the potential of digital technology to enhance knowledge and skills in educational institutions. The study also highlights the

importance of better infrastructure for online learning. India's insurance industry comprises 53 companies, with life insurance being the only public sector company. Life insurance is a long-term financial solution, with policyholders paying a premium in case of death or critical illness.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objectives of the present study are as follows

1. To analyze the impact of policyholders towards Economic development of LIC scheme in Salem City.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

- ❖ **H₀** : There is no association between satisfaction of policyholders towards Economic growth in services of LIC and mean rank of educational level of the respondents
- ❖ **H₀** : There is no association between satisfaction of policyholders towards Economic growth in services of LIC and mean rank of occupation of the respondents

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND RESEARCH DESIGN

Sources of Data

It utilizes two primary types of data: primary and secondary data. Primary data, obtained through surveys or direct observation, is the focus and is derived from new research conducted directly at the source. Various methods, including questionnaires and case studies, were employed for collecting the primary data, specifically acquired through a well-structured questionnaire administered to respondents in the selected research area of Salem City.

Sample Selected for the Study

The researcher opted for a convenient sampling method due to several reasons: the absence of a comprehensive list of policyholders provided by the local LIC office and the reluctance of some policyholders to partake, often stemming from a lack of awareness regarding the research's significance. However, some individuals were eager to provide data but were constrained by impatience.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Review of literature has significant relevance with any research work due to literature review the possibility of repetition of study can be eliminated and another dimension can be selected for the study. Many researchers have been conducted to analyze the various aspects of satisfaction of policyholders regarding the Economic growth within the Life Insurance Corporation. A number of studies are available and for the purpose of clarity the studies are reviewed and presented as follows.

Selvam, M. (2018). examined that This research assesses customer satisfaction with the Life Insurance Corporation in Chennai City, focusing on the services provided by LIC. Data was gathered from 150 policyholders through a questionnaire and analyzed using statistical tools like percentage calculations, chi-square, and ANOVA to understand factors influencing satisfaction levels with LIC's services.

Radhamani, S. (2013). analyzed that "Policyholder's satisfaction of private life insurance companies with reference to Tirupur District, Tamilnadu". Both public and private insurance companies now serve a vast clientele, leading to a significant increase in the number and scale of these enterprises across India. The shift from a "sellers market" to a "buyers market" characterizes this evolution, where the efficiency of the insurance sector depends on its capacity to deliver quality services meeting customer expectations. The primary goals of this research involve understanding the socio-economic characteristics of the sampled respondents and pinpointing the determinants influencing policyholder satisfaction within private life insurance companies. The methodology employed in this study relies on data analysis collected from 300 individual policyholders through the use of an interview schedule. This research exclusively gathered primary data, employing a simple random sampling method to obtain information from the three hundred sample respondents. The study's analysis identified that factors like Marital Status and Number of Policies held exhibit associations with policyholder satisfaction. In summary, this study aims to gauge various perspectives from policyholders and to assist

insurance companies in more effectively serving their policyholders with improved efficiency and quality service.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Socio - Demographic and Economic Profile of the Respondents

The Study furnishes the socio-demographic and economic profiles of the Life Insurance Corporation (LIC) policyholders, lending credibility to the collected data and offering an accurate portrayal of the studied population. This profile aids readers in gaining a comprehensive understanding of the respondents' backgrounds, cultural influences, and living standards, which significantly impact individual characteristics. The key variables analyzed in this section encompass gender, age, educational qualifications, occupation, marital status, monthly income, family size, and family type. Detailed descriptions elucidating the socio-demographic and economic profiles of the respondents are elaborated in the subsequent subsections of the study.

Table 1 – Economic Development of Policyholders towards Life Insurance Services

S.No	Factors	Classifications	N	Mean	Test Statistics		
					X2	df	P value
1	Gender	Male	111	86.24	10.348	1	0.000
		Female	89	67.74			
2	Age	Below 20 years	88	77.87	4.838	3	0.235
		20 – 30 years	31	88.26			
		31 – 40 years	48	75.05			
		Above 40 years	34	66.02			
3	Educational Qualification	Primary Level	48	94.30	13.439	3	0.000
		SSLC/HSC	76	87.98			
		Graduate	40	87.15			

		Diploma	36	62.13			
4	Occupation	Entrepreneur	41	72.03	16.986	4	0.002
		Non-Government Employee	47	76.46			
		Private Employee	40	87.40			
		Professionals	43	88.40			
		Others	29	74.28			
5	Marital Status	Married	113	86.88	11.166	1	0.000
		Unmarried	87	69.25			
6	Family Size	Below 3 members	79	92.85	10.333	2	0.003
		3 to 5 members	70	74.05			
		Above 5 members	51	67.88			
7	Monthly Income	Below Rs.200,000	54	77.14	14.383	3	0.000
		Rs.200,000 to Rs.30,000	55	87.94			
		Rs.30,001 to Rs.40,000	53	87.27			
		Above Rs.40,001	39	64.28			
8	Type of Family	Nuclear Family	141	97.67	5.823	1	0.512
		Joint Family	59	79.20			

SUGGESTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This section addresses the study's actionable suggestions in light of the observed results. Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations and proposals are offered. To satisfy the needs of the general public, LIC must periodically assess its plans and projects and make necessary adjustments. It is crucial to introduce new policies that have several advantages, such as tax breaks and high-quality customer support. In order to compete with private insurers, retain current policyholders, and draw in new ones, LIC must also modify its premium and bonus rates. It can be possible to accept premiums at any LIC of India branch. LIC can also

utilize viral marketing to promote more policies and raise awareness of its cutting-edge goods and services.

CONCLUSION

Customers now days have higher standards. What used to be able to meet their demands is no longer adequate. They look for items and services that are more valuable or that are innovative. In light of the growing rivalry and the increased demands of clients, LIC needs to continuously assess its services not just within its own sector but also in relation to other financial industries' best practices. At LIC, offering excellent customer service increases the possibility that clients would come back. It's critical for LIC to provide top-notch service and recognize the turning points for clients in the life insurance market. In the end, this results in increased client pleasure and loyalty, which is essential for generating revenue and growing their brand.

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